

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES ON THE COMPOSITION OF MANGANESE FERROCYANIDE COMPLEX

BY RAM SAHAI SAXENA

The formation and composition of manganese ferrocyanide has been studied by potentiometric titrations between manganese chloride and potassium ferrocyanide, using ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode, both by the direct and the inverse methods. The equivalence point obtained from the maximum value of dE/dC corresponds to the formation of a compound having the composition $4Mn_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_4Fe(CN)_6$, with either of the substances used as the reagent. The titration curves have a regular form; there is a sharp break in potential at the equivalence point and the results are accurate and reproducible. The effect of varying concentrations of alcohol on the end-point as well as on the nature of the curves has been studied.

The reaction between manganese salt and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ has been investigated by several workers by purely analytical methods and also by physico-chemical methods, but there is hardly any co-ordination of the views expressed by them. Stone and Van Ingen (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 19, 542) observed that the composition of manganese ferrocyanide corresponded to $K_2MnFe(CN)_6$, when $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was added to manganese salt and it changed to $K_4Mn_3[Fe(CN)_6]_3$, when precipitated in cold from an acid solution containing 5% HCl. Dickie (*ibid.*, 1902, 24, 1023) analysed manganese ferrocyanide by precipitating the compound in neutral and acidic solutions and observed that the percentage of Mn increased in the compound by adding an excess of manganese salt to $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, but when $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ was added in excess, the proportion of Mn in the compound decreased. Wyrubow (*Annalen*, 1835, 8, 444) suggested the formation of $K_2MnFe(CN)_6$ and also $Mn_3Fe(CN)_6$. Werner (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1909, 58, 23) obtained a white difficultly soluble compound $Mn_2Fe(CN)_6$. Britton and Dodd (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1543) titrated metal salts with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ conductometrically by means of a glass electrode and reported the formation of normal salt which was converted by further precipitant into $Mn_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot x K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (where x is less than 1). The combination might be either physical or chemical. Williams (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 28, 317) obtained $MnH_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4H_2O$ by treating manganese salts with $H_4Fe(CN)_6$. Eristavi and Barnabishvile (*J. Gen. Chem. USSR.*, 1936, 9, 1880) reported the formation of a flocculent precipitate of $K_2MnFe(CN)_6$.

In view of the conflicting opinions and in the absence of any decisive views on the composition of this compound, it was considered worthwhile to make its detailed study by physico-chemical investigations. The results provide more conclusive evidence on the composition of complex metallic ferro and ferricyanides (Saxena *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1956, 285, 90; 1954, 276, 204; this *Journal*, 1954, 81, 53, 157; 1952, 29, 263, 284, 529, 535; 1951, 28, 141, 221, 703). Whereas the composition of cobalt ferrocyanide and nickel ferrocyanide (Saxena, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 157, 21; this *Journal*,

1957, 34, 471) have already been studied, this paper incorporates the study on the composition of manganese ferrocyanide by potentiometric method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Merck's guaranteed extra pure reagents MnCl_2 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ were used. The strengths of the solutions were estimated by standard methods of analysis. Using different concentrations of the reactants, the titrations were performed both by the direct and the inverse methods *i.e.*, when $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution from the micro-burette was added to MnCl_2 solution in the electrode cell and *vice versa*. Potassium ferrocyanide solution containing 1% potassium ferricyanide was used to make the ferro-ferricyanide electrode (Kolthoff and Furman, "Potentiometric Titrations", New York, 1947, p. 323). A platinised platinum foil (*ibid.*, p. 204) was immersed in the solution of the titre and used as an indicator electrode in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode. The electrode cell was kept in an electrically maintained thermostat to control temperature. E.M.F. was measured on a Cambridge p_n -meter. The titrations were also carried out in presence of alcohol up to a total concentration of 20%. The potential between the platinum indicator electrode and the reference half-cell has been measured and plotted against the volume of the titrant. A sharp deflection in the curve occurs at the end-point which is marked by a pronounced maxima in dE/dV . (20 c.c. of the reagent was taken in the cell each time).

TABLE I

Summary of results of potentiometric titrations.

$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution (Molarity).	MnCl_2 solution (Molarity).	Points of equivalence.			
		c.c. of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ or MnCl_2 soln. required for the formation of $4\text{Mn}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.			
		Calc.	Obs. from dE/dV in presence of alcohol.		
			0%.	10%.	20%
Direct titrations (Figs. 1-2)					
M/5	M/20	4.375	4.34	4.36	4.38
M/20	M/100	3.50	3.44	3.46	3.48
Inverse titrations (Figs. 3-4)					
M/20	M/5	5.71	5.88	5.76	5.70
M/100	M/20	4.57	4.64	4.60	4.58

DISCUSSION

From the strengths of solution of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (M/5) and MnCl_2 (M/20), the calculated titre equivalents for the formation of more probable compounds are given below.

1. Titre value for 20 c.c. of M/20- MnCl_2 in direct titration	$\text{K}_2\text{MnFe}(\text{CN})_6$ 5.0 c.c. [M/5- $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution]	$\text{Mn}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ 2.5 c.c.	$4\text{Mn}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ 4.375 c.c.
2. Titre values for 20 c.c. of M/20- $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ in inverse titration	5.0 c.c. [M/5- MnCl_2 solution]	10 c.c.	5.71 c.c.

The titre values required for the formation of above compounds employing different concentrations of reactants can be calculated accordingly, both in the case of the direct and the inverse titrations.

It is clear from Figs. 1-4 that the reaction between $MnCl_2$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ can be successfully followed potentiometrically, applying ferro-ferricyanide electrode with either of the reactants alternately used as the titre. The point of inflection, calculated from the maxima in dE/dV , occurs at a stage where the molecular ratio of the reactants, $K_4Fe(CN)_6 : MnCl_2$ is as 7:8 and corresponds to the formation of the compound $4Mn_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3K_4Fe(CN)_6$ and is much different from those required for the formation of other probable compounds, $K_2MnFe(CN)_6$ and $Mn_2Fe(CN)_6$, as reported earlier in literature.

The titration curves have a regular shape; a sharp jump in potential occurs at the equivalence point and the results are accurate and reproducible. The E.M.F. becomes constant rapidly after each addition of the reagent in aqueous as well as in alcoholic medium, and the whole titration takes little time. The addition of alcohol improves the results (Table I), but it does not have any appreciable effect on the nature of curves or on the magnitude of the potential break in either case.

According to the equation $Fe(CN)_6^{4-} \rightleftharpoons Fe(CN)_6^{3-} + \ominus$, the oxidation potential of the ferricyanide-ferrocyanide electrode is given by

$$E = E_0 + 0.059 \log \frac{Fe(CN)_6^{4-}}{Fe(CN)_6^{3-}} \text{ at } 25^\circ.$$

In the titration of $MnCl_2$ with $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution containing a little ferricyanide, so long as there is an excess of Mn^{2+} ions in solution, the concentration of ferrocyanide is small, and so the potential of the electrode is high. As soon as manganese ions are

quantitatively precipitated, the next drop of ferrocyanide solution added causes an increase in $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ and, hence, a decrease in the oxidation potential occurs, indicating a sharp fall in direct titration curves at the end-point. Similarly, a marked upward jump in E. M. F. is observed at the equivalence point in the reverse titration curves due to the increase in the oxidation potential of the ferro-ferricyanide electrode.

It is to be noted that the titrations of MnCl_2 with $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ are accompanied by a marked change in colour at the equivalence point, *i.e.*, from greyish to white in direct titrations and from white to grey in reverse titrations. The change in colour is so sharp that the end-point can be accurately detected visually.

It is clear from Table I that the observed titre values in direct titrations are slightly lower than the calculated points of equivalence in aqueous medium; while in the case of inverse titrations they are slightly higher. In the presence of increasing amounts of alcohol, the observed titre values, both in the case of direct and inverse titrations, gradually approach the calculated values more closely.

The discrepancy between the observed and the calculated titre values in aqueous medium and the subsequent change when the titrations are carried out in alcoholic medium, support our views on the hydrolytic and adsorptive behaviour of such ferro- and ferricyanide complexes (*cf.* Saxena, previous publications).

In direct titrations, adsorption of Mn^{2+} ions by the precipitate would tend to lower the titre values in aqueous medium. In the inverse titrations, manganese ferrocyanide on hydrolysis would release some $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ ions which will consume some extra amount of MnCl_2 , howsoever little it may be and, hence, the amount of MnCl_2 required will be slightly greater than the calculated equivalent. Alcohol suppresses adsorption and hydrolysis and decreases the solubility of manganese ferrocyanide, and hence, a closer approach to the theoretical values is envisaged by the experimental results. In presence of 20% alcohol, the observed values almost coincide with the calculated titre values.

The results of potentiometric titrations suggest that manganese ferrocyanide is not a pure compound but a double salt represented by a $4\text{Mn}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and are in conformity with the observations of the author, obtained by applying other physico-chemical methods, such as conductometric and thermometric titrations (R.S. Saxena, *Proc. Indian Science Congress*, Part III, 1958, p. 93).

Quantitative work on adsorption and hydrolysis in the case of manganese ferrocyanide has been carried out and the results will be communicated shortly.